

Interactive Free Energy Relationship on the Oxidation of Aromatic Anils by Pyridinium Chlorochromate

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Bimolecular rate constants for the pyridinium chlorochromate oxidation of several substituted aromatic anils have been determined in aqueous acetic acid. The rate constants are found to be enhanced by electron-withdrawing substituents and retarded by electron-releasing substituents in both benzaldehyde and aniline rings. The magnitude of the ρ value obtained for various substituents in benzaldehyde moiety decreases with the introduction of electron-releasing groups in aniline moiety and vice versa. A linear plot is obtained between $\rho X(Y)$ (obtained from Hammett's plot for various substituents in benzaldehyde moiety) and σ_y (substituent constant for substituents in aniline moiety) with a slope of 0.44. The plot of $\rho Y(X)$ (obtained from Hammett's plot for various substituents in aniline moiety) versus σ_x (substituent constant for substituents in benzaldehyde moiety) is also linear with a slope of 0.46. The results have been analyzed in terms of interactive free energy relationship.

Aromatic anil ($X-CH=N-Y$) has two phenyl rings, X and Y. The ring X originates from benzaldehyde moiety and Y from aniline moiety. It is possible to evaluate the reaction constant (ρ) from the Hammett's plot by varying substituents in one of the rings X and Y, keeping the same substituent in the other ring. It is therefore possible to get several reaction constants for different substituents in one of the two rings. The purpose of the present investigation is to show that the multiple substituent effects in the oxidation of aromatic anils can be quantitatively analyzed in terms of an interactive free energy relationship by extending the classical Hammett relationship. Oxidation of aromatic anil by PCC was studied earlier¹. The reaction followed simple second order kinetics, being first order with respect to each of the reactants. Benzaldehyde and azobenzene were identified as the products. Herein we report the results of investigations on the oxidation of some *para*-substituted aromatic anils by PCC.

Results and Discussion

The effect of substituents on the rate was studied by varying the substituents in both the rings, i.e. X and Y (Table 1). In both the rings with H in the other ring, positive ρ values were obtained. This value increased when the substituent in the other ring was electron-withdrawing and decreased for electron-releasing substituents. The magnitude of ρ values is almost the same in rings X and Y. Reaction constants determined for various substituents in ring X for a particular substituent in ring Y and vice versa are given in Table 2.

The reaction constant values obtained in this study have been analyzed in terms of an interactive free energy relationship (IFER) for multiple substituent effect (MSE), as discussed by Argile and Ruasse² and Sondu *et al.*³, who suggested the following equation to be applicable for reactions of the above type,

$$[\rho Y(X) - \rho Y(X_0)] / \sigma_x = [\rho X(Y) - \rho X(Y_0)] / \sigma_y = q$$

where $\rho X(Y_0)$ and $\rho Y(X_0)$ are reaction constants for substituents in the ring X and Y respectively, for H in the other ring, $\rho X(Y)$ and $\rho Y(X)$ are reaction constants for various substituents in ring X and Y respectively, for a particular

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR VARIOUS SUBSTITUENTS IN BOTH THE RINGS OF ANILS IN THEIR OXIDATION

[Anil] = 1.5×10^{-2} M, [PCC] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, solvent = 3 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, $[H^+] = 1.5 \times 10^{-2}$ M, temp. = 30°

Substituents in benzaldehyde ring-X

	$10^2 k_2$ (s ⁻¹) for substituents in ring-Y*					
	<i>p</i> -OMe	<i>p</i> -Me	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
<i>p</i> -OMe	1.05	1.29	1.92	2.78	3.07	10.24
<i>p</i> -Me	1.33	1.62	2.59	3.41	3.49	15.49
H	1.65	2.41	3.65	6.02	6.47	24.82
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.87	3.91	6.04	10.91	10.96	50.12
<i>p</i> -Br	3.32	4.13	6.83	11.67	11.92	50.91
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	8.72	12.42	21.72	43.97	46.29	276.22

*Average of 3 experiments.

TABLE 2—HAMMETT ρ VALUES FOR SUBSTITUENTS IN ANIL

Substituents in ring-X	ρ -values for substituents in ring-X	Substituents in ring-Y	ρ -values for substituents in ring-Y
<i>p</i> -OMe	0.93	<i>p</i> -OMe	0.88
<i>p</i> -Me	0.99	<i>p</i> -Me	0.91
H	1.09	H	0.99
<i>p</i> -Cl	1.18	<i>p</i> -Cl	1.12
<i>p</i> -Br	1.21	<i>p</i> -Br	1.13
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.42	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.33

substituent in the other ring, while σ_x and σ_y are the substituent constants in rings X and Y. The ratios (q) are expected to be the same and constant (q is referred to as the cross-interaction constant). The above equation can be written as

$$[\rho Y(X) - \rho Y(X_0)] = q_x \sigma_x \text{ and } [\rho X(Y) - \rho X(Y_0)] = q_y \sigma_y$$

where q_x and q_y are the cross-interaction constants with respect to X and Y. These equations were found to be applicable to the present study as evidenced from the linear plots obtained when $\rho Y(X)/\rho X(Y)$ was plotted against σ_x/σ_y with slopes of q_x of 0.46 ($r = 0.991$) and q_y of 0.44 ($r = 0.989$) respectively. The q_x and q_y values are approximately equal, suggesting that the attack of PCC on the anil is a single concerted step and the substituted anils in each ring are oxidized by the same mechanism, as proposed in the case of oxidation of aromatic anils by acid bromate⁴, whose q_x and q_y are 0.75 and 0.70 respectively.

Experimental

Anils were prepared by literature method⁵ and its purity was checked by m.p. PCC was prepared and standardized⁶.

The iodometric method was followed for evaluating pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}). The bimolecular rate constant (k_2) was obtained from the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[Anil]$.

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